

Penetrating Foreign Body of Neck Involving-Subglottis: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Background: Penetrating neck injuries are not uncommon, while penetrated foreign bodies involving the larynx are rare. Both the types of injuries could be critical and challenging to the ENT surgeon. Penetrating neck injuries comprise of 05% to 10% of all trauma cases. Multiple vital structures are involved following such injuries as the neck is a relatively small anatomical area of the body. Surgical treatment is based on the zone involved. The neck is divided into three zones for convenience. Initially the general conditions of the patient with the neck injuries are assessed. Management varies from routine exploration to selective exploration. Injury to food and air passages and major blood vessels are commonly seen.

Aim of the Study: To present an unusual case of penetrating foreign body into the Neck in the area of Subglottic.

Materials: A 19-year-old man presented to our emergency outpatient clinic with pain in throat, hemoptysis and bleeding from anterior aspect of neck. He was construction worker who accidentally injured his neck while doing chipping work two hours prior to being shifted to the Emergency room.

Results: A thorough patient history taking was done and prompt imaging studies; CT scan and flexible fiberoptic laryngoscopy were done. An endoscopic approach was chosen, and the foreign body was found lodged in the posterior wall of the subglottic region and it was removed with foreign body grasping forceps.

Conclusions: Surgeons may be called on to manage penetrating neck injuries in the emergency room and hence be trained in skills enabling them to the following: 1. Assess and achieve an adequate and stable airway 2. Stabilize a collapsing circulation 3. Assess the head and neck injury swiftly in a logical manner prior to surgical exploration.

Keywords: Neck, Penetrating Injuries, Carotids, Food Passage and Airway.

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Introduction

Neck wounds are defined as those which extend deep to the platysma. [1] Penetrating neck injuries occur nearly in 05–10 % of all surgical trauma emergencies with a significant mortality. [2] Management consists of a logical approach with swift diagnostic assessment with protection of the adequate airway and circulation. [3] The wounds are associated with skeletal or neurological damage requiring surgical intervention. [4] Penetrating neck injuries are not uncommon, usually presenting with obvious and specific traumatic history, such as gun shot or stabbing. [5]

The lack of proper and prompt treatment might lead to the development of fatal consequences compromising the airway of the patient. However, incidences of penetrated foreign bodies involving the larynx are rare, and only few relevant published reports are present in the literature. The first reported case was of a child who died from sequential abscess formation in 1885. [6] The initial symptoms of penetrating neck injuries are diverse, including neck pain, emphysema, stridor, dysphagia, dyspnea, and hoarseness. [7]

Herein, we present a unique case of a patient who was penetrated with a piece of metal in the subglottic region, presenting to the clinic with pain and hemoptysis. Classifying the neck zone involvement (zone i, zone ii, or zone iii), mechanism of injury, and velocity of the projectile is helpful in determining the risk of major injury and need for surgical exploration versus imaging and/or observation. [8] In contrast to the zone approach, many institutions have adopted a selective approach to surgical exploration of penetrating neck injuries to reduce unnecessary operative interventions. [9] Regardless of the approach, emergent surgical exploration is necessary for immediate life-threatening signs or symptoms. [10] Stable patients with non-emergent injuries benefit from multi slice helical computed tomography as an initial screening test to detect and characterize cervical, vascular, and aerodigestive injuries.[11] Hemodynamic and neurologic status should be monitored closely for at least 48 to 72 hours in patients who are asymptomatic. Therefore,

imaging and close observation are also important. In this case study, we describe rare instance of penetrating foreign body in subglottis.

Case Report:

A 19 year old man presented to our emergency outpatient clinic with pain in throat, hemoptysis and bleeding from anterior aspect of neck. He was construction worker who accidentally injured his neck while doing chipping work two hours prior to being shifted to the Emergency room. The flying sharp object had created a penetrating wound in his anterior aspect of neck. Initially, the wound bled a little but soon stopped spontaneously. However, patient had pain in the throat and one episode of hemoptysis had prompted him to visit the hospital for evaluation. No other symptoms were observed, such as odynophagia, dysphagia, dyspnea, and cough or choking episode. The patient's medical history was unremarkable. He was a smoker and social drinker.

Figure 1: Showing the Patient with penetrating neck wound. (Schematic figure showing the levels of penetrating injuries: Zone I, II and III)

Physical examination of the Neck revealed a laceration of size 0.2cmx 0.2 cm over anterior aspect of the neck. A flexible fiberoptic laryngoscope revealed an impacted foreign body in the posterior wall of subglottic region of the patient. The vocal cords were mobile and no palsy was noted. X-ray neck demonstrated a radiopaque

foreign body at the level of C5- C6 most probably embedded in subglottic region, or probably in the oesophagus. The adjacent vascular structures were not involved. No subcutaneous air was present. The routine blood investigation was done showed normal results.

Figure 2: Showing the Fibreoptic endoscopy images of the Larynx, Trachea

Figure 3: Showing the X-Ray Neck AP and Lateral Views

Figure 4: Showing the Intra-Operative Endoscopic pictures:

Discussion

Penetrating neck injuries are usually complicated involving multiple vital structures, like vascular channels, upper respiratory tract, digestive tract, and neurological structures; accounting to 30% of the total penetrating neck injuries. In a review

series by Roon A.J., Christensen N et al. [12] penetrating Laryngotracheal injuries comprised of 08% of the total penetrating neck injuries. Excluding military experiences, the mortality rate from penetrating neck wound was 03.7%- 05.9%. However, this mortality rate would increase to 30%, once vascular or other major anatomical

structures were involved. [13] As a result, comprehensive evaluation and prompt treatment are crucial in penetrating neck injuries. Laryngotracheal injuries due to puncture-causing foreign bodies are uncommon and can lead to significant morbidity and mortality rates. [14] A thorough patient history taking, using prompt and ideal imaging studies such as CT scan and flexible fibre optic laryngoscopy, can help establish the right diagnosis. [16] Further evaluation by arteriography or esophagography are required if associated structures are involved. Early mortality is greatly influenced by airway management. [15] Patients with major laryngeal injuries usually require tracheostomy or cricothyroidotomy. Immediate exploration and surgical intervention are essential in severe symptomatic cases. [16]

However, our case presented without any trivial symptoms. The surgical approaches to remove the penetrating foreign bodies from the neck are transcervical and endoscopic; either bronchoscopic or Esophageal approach to remove the foreign body is optional. [17] A successful removal depends on the accurate localization of the foreign body and choosing the appropriate method. [18] In our case, the foreign body was localized by pre-operating X-Ray and flexible bronchoscopy and intra-operative direct laryngoscopy. The foreign body was removed by endoscopic approach. An external approach provides a clear identification of the involved anatomical structures and establishment of surgical drainage requirement.

The treatment approach should be tailored on Individual case basis. [19] As soon as a patient with penetrating neck injury comes to the emergency room, rapid assessment of the airway, breathing, and circulation are essential. [20] Once the patient is stabilized, a second survey is carried out checking for symptoms and signs of subcutaneous emphysema, hoarseness, stridor, and respiratory distress and external injuries to the neck are made. [21] The following are anatomic areas of the neck (Fig. 5): & Zone 1—between the sternal notch and the cricoid cartilage & Zone 2—between the cricoid cartilage and the mandibular angle & Zone 3—between the mandibular angle and the skull base. Zone 1 consists of the major vascular structures of the subclavian artery and vein, jugular vein, and common carotid artery, as well as the esophagus, thyroid, and trachea. Zone 2 consists of the common carotid artery, internal and external carotid arteries, jugular vein, larynx, hypopharynx, and cranial nerves X, XI, and XII. Zone 3 consists of the internal and external carotid arteries, jugular vein, lateral pharynx, and cranial nerves VII, IX, X, XI, and XII. [22] Approximately 20–30 % cases have laryngeal, tracheal, or esophageal injury. [23]

Injury to carotids and subclavian vessels carry a higher incidence of mortality. [24]

Penetrating injuries affecting the Airway tract consists of symptoms of increased respiratory rate and signs of airway distress, including dyspnea and stridor, requiring immediate assessment, and if necessary a tracheostomy has to be done to prevent death. [25] Vocal (Speech) quality of the patients should be noted, and the patients should be questioned about their voice changes. The neck and upper chest should be palpated for subcutaneous emphysema, and the larynx and trachea should be palpated for tenderness and crepitus. [26] Whenever laryngotracheal injury is suspected, intubation should be carried out with great care as further damage to the airway may occur and false passages can be created. (27) Controlled tracheostomy under local anesthesia is always preferred. Flexible laryngoscopy, CT imaging, direct laryngoscopy, and tracheoscopy are done. [28]

An unstable circulation and free bleeding from the wound or marked swelling of the neck may indicate injury to the great vessels. Therefore, all cases of neck injuries should have a check on distal pulse and bruit. [29] Angiography may be done in hemodynamically stable patients prior to exploration where significant damage to vessels is suspected. This can remain hidden in some cases following the traumatic event. Injury to Esophagus and Pharynx Bleeding from the mouth, drooling, and subcutaneous emphysema are all signs suggestive of upper digestive tract injury. Contrast-enhanced study may be done if injury is suspected. [30]

Indication of immediate surgical intervention in penetrating neck injuries includes hemodynamic instability, exsanguinations hemorrhage, or expanding hematoma. All patients who are stable must have a thorough evaluation of the vascular structures and of the aero-digestive tract prior to any surgical intervention. [31] For Zone 1 neck injuries a consultation with a thoracic surgeon may be required, where resection of clavicle and mediastinotomy, or a formal lateral thoracotomy is required. [32] Zone 2 penetrating injuries of the neck may require the all the neck veins to be ligated and wherever necessary the internal jugular vein may have to be repaired if found damaged with the opposite side vein intact. [33] The external carotid artery may have to be ligated to stop severe hemorrhage in few cases. [34] The common carotid artery and the internal carotid artery if injured must be repaired wherever possible, minimizing any period of arterial clamping and avoiding this where the circulation on the other side is compromised. [35] A lateral arteriorrhaphy or end-to-end anastomosis or grafting is done in partial injuries. Zone 3 Vascular injuries are difficult to access

surgically and may require mandibular subluxation or mandibulotomy for exposure. [36]50 % of patients with airway injuries were found to have obviously injuries to the pharynx and oesophagus. [37] Tracheostomy is done if there is airway compromise. Laryngeal injuries are classified by location (supraglottic, transglottic, cricoid, or tracheal) and type (hematoma, mucosal tears or lacerations, cartilage fractures and/or dislocations, or laryngotracheal disruption). [38] Minor lacerations, small hematomas, and undisplaced single fractures may be managed with observation and serial examination.[12, 29 and 24] Lacerations which need exploration and repaired as follows: (a) involving the anterior commissure with exposed cartilage (b) multiple or displaced cartilage fractures (c) vocal cord immobility or arytenoid dislocation (d) injuries sufficient to cause airway compromise Fig. 5 Showing the anatomic areas of neck Indian J Surg (January–February 2013) 75(1):43–46 45

Conclusions

Penetrating laryngeal injuries are rare but can be critical and challenging even for experienced physicians. A systematic evaluation, including contrast-enhanced CT and laryngoscopy, is helpful in injury localization and preoperative planning. A proper airway management and surgical approach minimizes the postoperative morbidity and mortality rate. Finally, befitting protective equipment is indispensable for workers with potentially hazardous careers.

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